

NO AVAILABLE GUIDELINES

Currently, no collaborations or guidelines for publishing systematic reviews or meta-analyses on agricultural or soil issues exist

SUPPORT CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Agricultural management practices can support carbon sequestration and, therefore, offer potential removal strategies whilst also improving overall soil quality

POOR-QUALITY!

Too many articles apply less rigorous methodologies. As a result, poor-quality meta-analyses are published, leading to questionable conclusions and recommendations to scientists, policymakers, and farmers
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15064441

AUTHORS

Julia Fohrafellner, Sophie Zechmeister-Boltenstern, Rajasekaran Murugan, Elena Valkama (2023)

QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF META-ANALYSES ON SOIL ORGANIC CARBON

Urgent need for improved meta-analysis

On the effects of organic agriculture, biochar, fertilization, or crop diversification on SOC.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply.

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

11000+ scientists, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL WORK PACKAGE 7 SYNTHESIS & KNOWLEDGE

The purpose of work package 7 is to streamline a feedback loop of information towards the roadmap, develop online resources on Agricultural Soil Management for the Future, and design capacity building for farmers and advisors to upscale implementation of climatesmart sustainable soil management.

WORK PACKAGE LEADER

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Understanding how soil-carbon sequestration can contribute to climate change mitigation at the regional level and accounting for carbon.

MISSION SOIL: conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL Work package 7

Synthesis and knowledge application

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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